

Alkaloids of *Heliotropium indicum*

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Three pyrrolizidine alkaloids, acetylasiocarpine, europine and heliosupine has been isolated from the whole plant of *Heliotropium indicum*. This is the first report of these alkaloids in *Heliotropium indicum*.

The plant *Heliotropium indicum* is distributed throughout India and used in Indian System of Medicine as diuretics, in the treatment of ulcers, wounds and boils¹. A number of pyrrolizidine alkaloids²⁻⁵ together with non-alkaloidal constituents^{6,7} have earlier been reported from this plant. Here we report the isolation of further alkaloids, acetylasiocarpine, europine and heliosupine from the whole plant of *Heliotropium indicum*.

The whole plant (4 kg) was collected locally and dried material was extracted MeOH in a soxhlet extractor. The methanolic extract (150 g) was stirred with 7% aqueous citric acid. The aqueous acidic solution was basified with NH₄OH and extracted with CHCl₃ which gave a brown gummy mass of crude bases (18 g). The crude bases were chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. The eluted fractions were monitored by TLC at every stage for their homogeneity. The eluants from CHCl₃-MeOH (4 : 1), (1 : 1) and (1 : 4) on repeated crystallisation and prep. TLC furnished the alkaloids : acetylasiocarpine as oil (22 mg), $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 1^\circ$ (c. 2.0, EtOH); europine, amorphous powder (31 mg), $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 10.8^\circ$ (c. 2.3, CHCl₃) and heliosupine as gum (25 mg).

Acetylasiocarpine : It exhibited IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3650, 1735, 1715 cm⁻¹; MS m/z 453 [M⁺] (C₂₃H₃₅NO₈); 400 MHz ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 5.70 (br s, H-2), 3.30, 3.82 (m, each, H-3), 2.75, 3.12 (m, each, H-5), 1.85 (m, H-6), 5.00 (m, H-7), 4.00 (br s, H-8), 4.89 (AB q, *J* 14 Hz, H-9), 3.76 (q, *J* 6 Hz, H-3'), 1.20 (d, *J* 6 Hz, H-4'), 1.50 (s, H-6'), 1.50 (s, H-7'), 3.20 (s, H-8'), 5.90 (q, *J* 7 Hz, H-3''), 1.92 (d, *J* 7 Hz, H-4''), 1.80 (s, H-5''), 2.10 (s, CH₃CO-); 100 MHz ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 135.0 (C-1), 128.4 (C-2), 62.2 (C-3), 54.2 (C-5),

30.6 (C-6), 78.8 (C-7), 78.4 (C-8), 62.10 (C-9), 173.5 (C-1'), 83.9 (C-2'), 78.3 (C-3'), 13.1 (C-4'), 85.0 (C-5'), 26.5 (C-6'), 24.8 (C-7'), 56.4 (C-8'), 167.3 (C-1''), 127.8 (C-2''), 137.8 (C-3''), 15.9 (C-4''), 20.2 (C-5''), 30.2 (CH₃CO-), 195.1 (CH₃CO-). The above data tallies with acetylasiocarpine⁸⁻¹⁰ which was proved by co-TLC with authentic sample. **Europine** : It exhibited IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3540, 1715 cm⁻¹; MS m/z 329 [M⁺] (C₁₆H₂₇NO₆); 400 MHz ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 5.62 (br s, H-2), 3.22, 3.78 (m, each, H-3), 2.50, 3.12 (m, each, H-5), 1.77, 1.89 (m, each, H-6), 4.00 (m, H-7), 3.90 (br s, H-8), 4.76, 4.90 (AB q, each, *J* 14 Hz, H-9), 3.72 (q, *J* 6 Hz, H-3'), 1.15 (d, *J* 6 Hz, H-4'), 1.20 (s, H-6'), 1.11 (s, H-7'), 3.23 (s, H-8'); 100 MHz ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) 135.0 (C-1), 125.2 (C-2), 61.5 (C-3), 53.8 (C-5), 33.6 (C-6), 74.2 (C-7), 78.9 (C-8), 62.0 (C-9), 173.6 (C-1'), 84.0 (C-2'), 78.7 (C-3'), 12.3 (C-4'), 73.0 (C-5'), 26.0 (C-6'), 24.8 (C-7'), 55.5 (C-8'). The compound was identified as europine^{9,10} on comparison of the above data with reported data. **Heliosupine** : It exhibited IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3500, 1710 cm⁻¹; MS m/z 397 [M⁺] (C₂₀H₃₁NO₇); 400 MHz ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 5.76 (br s, H-2), 3.30, 3.90 (m, each, H-3), 2.76, 3.18 (m, each, H-5), 1.88 (m, H-6), 5.00 (m, H-7), 4.08 (br s, H-8), 4.86 (q, *J* 14 Hz, H-9), 3.72 (q, *J* 6 Hz, H-3'), 1.20 (d, *J* 6 Hz, H-4'), 1.22 (s, H-6'), 1.10 (s, H-7'), 6.05 (q, *J* 7 Hz, H-3''), 1.94 (d, *J* 7 Hz, H-4''), 1.79 (s, H-5''); 100 MHz ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ 135.0 (C-1), 128.1 (C-2), 62.3 (C-3), 54.3 (C-5), 30.5 (C-6), 76.3 (C-7), 78.2 (C-8), 62.2 (C-9), 173.8 (C-1'), 83.6 (C-2'), 78.4 (C-3'), 12.8 (C-4'), 72.6 (C-5'), 26.6 (C-6'), 24.7 (C-7'), 167.8 (C-1''), 127.9 (C-2''), 138.5 (C-3''), 16.0 (C-4''), 20.4 (C-5''). These data were in perfect agreement with the reported data of heliosupine^{9,10}.

The isolation of acetylasiocarpine, europine and heliosupine are the first report from *H. indicum*.

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